

Spectrophotometric Study of the Complexation Reaction Between Uranium (VI) and Salicylanilide

B. S. PANNU, B. S. SEKHON and S. L. CHOPRA

Department of Chemistry & Biochemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana

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Salicylanilide forms orange yellow coloured complex with uranium ion in a 50% aqueous ethanol at pH 7.0 ± 0.1 which has been studied spectrophotometrically. The results of Job's method, molar ratio method and limiting logarithmic method indicate 1 : 1 composition for the complex which has a maximum absorbance at 420 nm and obeys Beer's law in the range of 1 to 40 μg of uranium (VI) per ml. The apparent stability constant of the complex is 4.74 at $20^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

A LARGE number of reagents have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium (VI)¹⁻⁸. Salicylanilide has been found to form an orange yellow coloured complex with uranyl ion and, therefore, it was considered desirable to study the complexation reaction between uranium (VI) and salicylanilide. Thus the present paper describes the results on the composition, stability and other analytical characteristics of the complex formed by uranium (VI) with salicylanilide.

Experimental

Salicylanilide was prepared and purified by the method of Wagner⁹. Standard solutions of this reagent were prepared in pure ethanol. All other chemicals used were of BDH analytical grade.

The stock solution of uranium (VI) was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of pure uranyl acetate (BDH) in double distilled water. The concentration of uranium (VI) in the solution was determined by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. Dilute solutions of desired concentrations were obtained, as and when needed from this stock solution.

Absorbance measurements were made with Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. The pH measurements of the solutions were recorded with 'Systronic' pH meter using glass and calomel electrodes with an accuracy of 0.05 pH. All measurements were carried out at $20^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ in 50% aqueous ethanol.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH and time on complex formation :

A mixture containing 1×10^{-5} moles of the metal and 2×10^{-4} moles of salicylanilide was taken in series of 25 ml measuring flasks. The pH values of these solutions were adjusted in the range of 5.40 to 8.70

by the addition of dilute solutions of ammonium hydroxide or acetic acid. The volume in each case was made to 25 ml. Then absorbance measurements were carried out at 420 nm. The curve obtained by plotting the absorbance vs pH is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the absorbance changes markedly with the change in pH of the solution. The pH range of the maximum absorbance is very narrow, from 6.9 to 7.1. It was noted that there was no change in absorbance over a period of 48 hr at pH 7.0 ± 0.1 . However, coloured complex does not appear if the pH of the medium is either below 5 or above 9.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on absorbance.

Composition of the chelate :

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹⁰ was employed for the determination of the nature of the complexes formed in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol solution. Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mole ratio of uranium (VI) to salicylanilide were

prepared keeping the total volume 25 ml and adjusting the pH at 7.0 ± 0.1 in each case. Absorbance measurements were carried out at 420 nm. It was observed that in all the cases only one complex was formed.

The composition of the uranium(VI) salicylanilide complex was studied by three different methods :

- i) Job's Method of continuous variation¹¹ using equimolar solutions.
- ii) Mole ratio method¹².
- iii) Limiting logarithmic method of Bent and French.¹³

Job's method of equimolar solutions (Fig. 2), showed that the stoichiometric ratio of uranium (VI) to salicylanilide is 1 : 1. The molar ratio method (Fig. 3) and limiting logarithmic method of Bent and French (Fig. 4) confirm the 1 : 1 composition of the complex.

Fig. 2. Job's method for composition
 Conc. of U(VI) solution : $1 \times 10^{-3}M$
 Conc. of reagent solution : $1 \times 10^{-3}M$.

Stability constant of the complex :

The apparent stability constant of the complex was determined by limiting logarithmic method of Bent and French. The value of log K is 4.7 ± 0.1 at 20° which shows that the complex is highly stable

Sensitivity :

The values of sensitivity were found to be $0.08 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (practical) and $0.008 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (Sandell). This shows that the reagent is sensitive to be used as a colorimetric reagent for spectrophotometric determination of uranium (VI).

Beer's Law :

Equal volumes of solutions containing the same concentration ($1 \times 10^{-5}M$) of salicylanilide were taken in 25 ml measuring flasks. Varying concentrations of uranyl ion ranging from 5×10^{-6} moles to 2×10^{-4} moles were then added to the flasks. The pH of the solutions was adjusted to 7.0 ± 0.1 adding dilute ammonium hydroxide or acetic acid keeping the volume to 25 ml in each case. The optical densities were measured at 420 nm against reagent blank.

It is seen from Fig. 5 that Beer's law is obeyed from 1 to 40 μg of uranium (VI) per ml of the solution.

Fig. 3. Molar ratio method.

Analytical Studies of the complex :

The colour formation of the complex is instantaneous. The colour intensity of the complex is stable even after 48 hr of standing in the temperature

ranging from 10° to 40°. The effect of the addition of salicylanilide in different concentrations was studied and it was observed that fivefold excess of it is necessary to have maximum colour formation.

Effect of Ions :

A large number of standard solutions containing anions and cations were prepared. The effect of these ions on the optical density of the system was studied. It was found that Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , VO^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} interfere at all concentrations in the formation of the coloured complex and should be removed if this reaction is to be studied quantitatively.

The ions like Na^+ , K^+ , Mn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , La^{3+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Cl^- , CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- did not interfere in the determination of uranium by measurement of optical density.

Procedure recommended for colorimetric determination :

To the solution of uranyl ion containing uranium (VI) upto 40 μg is added a fivefold excess of salicylanilide. In order to maintain the pH at 7.0 ± 0.1

Fig. 4. Limiting logarithmic method
I. Ligand Constant
II. Metal Constant.

few drops of dilute ammonium hydroxide or acetic acid should be used. The optical density is measured at 420 nm after shaking the mixture solution. The concentration of the unknown sample solution can

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Fig. 5. Beer's Law.

then be obtained by comparing absorbance of the unknown solution with the calibration curve obtained earlier.

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